

December 12, 2024

This document presents Extended Data and Figures 1 and 2 related to the F1000 Data Note, "A Guide to Selecting High-Performing Antibodies for S1PR1 (UniProt ID: P21453) for Use in Western Blot, Immunoprecipitation, and Immunofluorescence."

Extended Data - Figure 1: S1PR1 antibody screening by western blot.

Lysates of SK-HEP-1 WT and *S1PR1* KO were prepared, and 40 µg of protein were processed for western blot with the indicated S1PR1 antibodies. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are presented to show equal loading of WT and KO lysates and protein transfer efficiency from the acrylamide gels to the nitrocellulose membrane. Antibody dilutions were chosen according to the recommendations of the antibody supplier. An exception was given for antibody 63335** which was titrated to improve signal. Antibody dilution used: ab233386** at 1/1000, A12935 at 1/1500, ARP80838 at 1/500., NBP2-67129** at 1/1000, 63335** at 1/500, 55133-1-AP at 1/1000, MA5-32587** at 1/1000, MA5-35431** at 1/1000, MA5-38484* at 1/500. Predicted band size: 42.8 kDa. *= monoclonal antibody, **= recombinant antibody.

Extended Data - Figure 2: S1PR1 antibody performance analysis in immunofluorescence.

A semiautomated image analysis of S1PR1 antibody performance at two different dilutions per antibody was conducted on a mosaic culture of WT and KO cells using custom in-house scripts that leverage the Cellpose algorithm and FIJI (ImageJ) software. The analysis included at least 500 WT and KO cells. The specific names of the anti-S1PR1 antibodies used are indicated. Cell segmentation was conducted using a Python script that applied Cellpose1.0 to both cell mask channels. An ImageJ macro generated cell mask outlines and performed background signal subtraction on the antibody channel using minimum intensity projection. Processed images were overlaid with cell mask outlines in the antibody channel, and fluorescence intensity was quantified within the segmented cells. All scripts are publicly available on the YCharOS GitHub repository. The histogram shows the antibody intensity ratio of WT cells to KO cells, with each dot corresponding to the intensity ratio of a single cell. Antibodies yielding a ratio of approximately 1.0 are not specific to S1PR1.

